

HOME YARD CARBON GARDENING

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Carbon gardening refers to all activities that can improve the carbon sequestration and storage of vegetation in the yard. Individual yards do not make a big difference, but small houses cover a significant proportion of urban land area.

The information in this booklet is based on scientific knowledge produced in the CO-CARBON project and the practical experiences of Finnish home gardeners in 2021–2023. Although the booklet is designed for the needs of private homeowners, it can also be used in the yards of housing cooperatives and commercial buildings. The booklet explains six elements of carbon gardening related to vegetation that are accessible to all residents and gives maintenance recommendations.

The booklet will give ideas on how, with only small changes, an ordinary yard could be turned into a yard that sequesters and stores carbon.

Six key elements of carbon gardening:

1. Permeable surfaces

Where are the water-permeable, plant-covered surfaces in the yard?

2. Multi-layered vegetation

Are there areas in the yard where trees, bushes and ground-covering plants grow together?

3. Living soil

Is there room in the yard for worms and other important soil organisms?

4. Covered soil surface

Where are the areas in the yard that are regularly raked and weeded?

5. Twigs, leaves, and shredded grass

Where does the organic matter of the yard end up?

6. Multipurpose vegetation

How many different tasks do plants have in the yard? Can they also participate in carbon sequestration?

1. PERMEABLE SURFACES

The permeable, plant-covered surfaces of the yard form a connection between soil, vegetation, and air. Permeable surfaces enable the circulation of carbon, nutrients, and water through vegetation and allow soil-air interaction and water absorption. Impermeable surfaces, such as asphalt and dense pavement, break the connection.

2. MULTI-LAYERED VEGETATION

Plants take carbon dioxide from the atmosphere through their stomata in the leaves and needles. The more leaf surface area there is in the garden, the more carbon dioxide can be bound from the atmosphere. Multi-layeredness means a planting area that combines trees, bushes, and ground cover plants of different heights.

3. LIVING SOIL

Small organisms in the soil, such as microbes, are part of the carbon cycle. Micro-organisms convert organic carbon into a permanent part of the soil's carbon storage, while releasing carbon back into the atmosphere through respiration. Plant cover, a diverse root system, organic fertilizers, and adequate moisture provide a good habitat for soil micro-organisms.

4. COVERED SOIL SURFACE

The open soil surface does not sequester atmospheric carbon. The bases of plantations, hedgerows, and rose gardens have been typically kept open. The care of vegetable garden has also been based on open topsoil, for example by weeding row gaps and turning the soil in autumn.

5. TWIGS, LEAVES AND SHREDDED GRASS

Carbon stored in different parts of the plant should not be removed from the garden. Dead parts of trees and shrubs and softer growth from the same year decompose at different rates, so they can be used in different ways in the yard. A composter is not always needed to recycle biomass on-site.

6. MULTIFUNCTIONAL VEGETATION

Garden plants have different functions. Multifunctionality means combining different functions in a single plant. Plants can act as space dividers, screens, ramp binders, decoration, and useful plants in the yard. At the same time, they provide ecosystem services, one of which is carbon sequestration. Carbon sequestration works best when vegetation is thriving.

More information: cocarbon.fi

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